

MONITORING OF FATIGUE INDUCED PROPAGATING DELAMINATIONS USING EMBEDDED FIBRE BRAGG GRATING SENSORS AND OPERATIONAL MODAL PARAMETER ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

Due to their complex architecture, composite laminates can experience different types of faults, among which delaminations are the most frequent. Although delamination onset is due to different reasons, delamination propagation is mainly caused by fatigue. Often, propagating delaminations can lead to catastrophic events, and thus systems for delamination monitoring are required. Many monitoring methods based on different types of sensor systems have been proposed. The modal analysis method is one of these. Such method uses the changes of the modal parameters, such as natural frequencies, as features for damage identification and monitoring. To retrieve the modal parameters, vibration measurements are needed. Fibre Bragg gratings (FBG) sensors are suitable to accomplish this task, especially in the case of composite materials, since they can be embedded and multiplexed. FBG sensors combined with modal analysis techniques have already been used to detect cracks and delaminations. However, no study exists where operational modal analysis and embedded FBG sensors have been used for real time monitoring of delaminations which propagate under fatigue loading. Using a composite laminated beam with two embedded FBG sensors and one initial delamination, we performed real time monitoring of the delamination size by analyzing the shifts induced by the delamination growth in the beam natural frequencies. To make the delamination propagate, we applied fatigue load cycles on the beam using an electromechanical shaker. During the loading, we acquired the strain time histories by demodulating the FBG output signals. At the same time, for sake of comparison, we measured the out of plane beam accelerations using a surface mounted accelerometer. Successively, we calculated the beam modal parameters using a polyreference least-square modal parameter estimator. This paper reports the shifts of the natural frequencies computed during the delamination propagation. The natural frequencies obtained from the FBG sensors and the accelerometer are in good agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is a process that involves the use of one or more non-destructive evaluation (NDE) systems to observe and monitor over time the state of health of a structural system. SHM technologies are fundamental, not only for assessing the safety and durability of structures, but also for decreasing the maintenance costs and the downtime. The increasing use of composite materials has made the SHM process even more challenging than in the past. Composite materials are in fact anisotropic and can show different failure mechanisms, such as delaminations, cracks and fibre-matrix debonding.

Several sensors based on different sensing principle are available to monitor composites. Among these, fibre Bragg grating sensors are one of the most promising. In fact, due to their reduced dimensions and weight, FBGs are suitable to be embedded in composite materials during the manufacturing process. Besides their low intrusivity, FBG sensors offer other advantages. For instance, they allow spatial multiplexing of several sensors by using only one optical fibre; they are also resistant to corrosion and high temperature and they are immune to electromagnetic disturbances. Compared to surface mounted sensors, embedded FBGs provide the additional benefit of measuring the internal physical state of the composite material, which is of great relevance in the detection of damages (such as delaminations) occurring beneath the laminate top surface.

Numerous application of FBG sensors for damage detection in composite materials have been reported in literature [1-8]. However, in most of these studies the FBG sensors have been used under static and/or quasi-static loading conditions and the damage assessment has been based on the analysis of the measured local strain levels. Only recently, researchers have started to investigate the feasibility of using FBG sensors for vibration based damage detection purposes. Some authors, for instance, have started to combine FBGs with modal analysis techniques, which are capable to show the presence of structural damages by monitoring the alterations induced in the modal parameters (i.e. eigenfrequencies, damping, eigenvectors). In 2002, Watkins et al. [8] used surface mounted optic fibre sensors and neural network to detect and locate delaminations in composite beams by analysing the shifts induced in the beam modal frequencies. More recently, Cusano et al. [9] employed embedded fibre Bragg grating to perform experimental modal analysis of an aircraft model wing, while Capoluongo et al. [10] showed that FBGs can detect resonant modes frequency and amplitude variations up to a frequency of 1.5 kHz.

In this paper, we investigate the use of embedded FBG sensors to monitor the modal frequencies shifts induced by a delamination which propagates in a composite beam subjected to fatigue load. Using a carbon fibre reinforced (CFR) beam with two embedded FBG sensors and one initial delamination, we succeeded in tracking the delamination size by accurately monitoring the shifts of the modal frequencies. To make the delamination propagate, we applied a fatigue load using an electro-mechanical shaker. During the loading, we acquired the local strain time histories by demodulating the FBG output signals with an in house recently developed algorithm [11,12]. At the same time, for sake of comparison, we measured the out of plane beam accelerations using a surface mounted accelerometer. Successively, we calculated the beam modal parameters using a state-of-the-art modal parameter estimator (the so called polyreference least-square [13]). This paper reports the shifts of the natural frequencies computed during the delamination propagation. The natural frequencies obtained from the FBG sensors and the accelerometer are in good agreement. All computed natural frequencies decrease as the delamination size increase.

This paper is further structured as follows. Section 2 recalls the FBG working principle and introduces the algorithm used for the demodulation of the FBG signals (the so called fast phase correlation method). Section 3 describes the manufacturing of the test beam together with the experimental setup and procedure. Section 4 contains the experimental results and the author comments while Section 5 is dedicated to the conclusive remarks and the planned future work.

2 FIBRE BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

2.1 Fibre Bragg grating working principle

A fibre Bragg grating is a particular type of optical fibre with a grating inscribed inside the fibre

core region by means of UV light. In the grating region the refractive index of the fibre undergoes a periodic modulation. As a result, when broadband light is transmitted into the optical fibre, the grating acts as a wavelength selective filter that reflects only a particular wavelength. This wavelength is called Bragg wavelength λ_B and is given by

$$\lambda_B = 2 n_{\text{eff}} \Lambda \quad (1)$$

where n_{eff} is the effective refractive index averaged over the grating length L and Λ is the grating pitch (Figure 1). Changes in the Bragg wavelength are due to changes in either of both n_{eff} and Λ . For instance, when a mechanical load is applied to the fibre (Figure 1), the grating pitch Λ varies and consequently the Bragg wavelength shifts in the wavelength space. The sensitivity of the Bragg wavelength to the axial strain acting in the fibre is expressed by the following equation

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = (1 - p_{\text{eff}})\epsilon_{zz} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{zz} is the strain induced in the fibre axial direction and p_{eff} is the effective photo elastic coefficient. The p_{eff} can be experimentally determined. A typical value of p_{eff} for GeO₂ doped (quartz) glass fibre is 0.204.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the working principle of a fibre Bragg grating sensor

2.2 The novel fast phase correlation demodulation algorithm

It is possible to retrieve the strain acting on a FBG sensor by tracking the shift of the Bragg wavelength. Different peak tracking algorithms exist in literature. In this research article, the novel Fast Phase Correlation (FPC) [11] algorithm is used. The FPC algorithm computes the wavelength shift between two FBG reflected spectra $R(\lambda)$ and $R'(\lambda) = R(\lambda + \Delta\lambda)$ by means of the following equation

$$\Delta\lambda = \text{mean}_{2 \leq k \leq M} \left((\angle \mathcal{F}\{R'(k)\} - \angle \mathcal{F}\{R(k)\}) \frac{N k \delta\lambda}{2\pi} \right) \quad (3)$$

In Equation 3, the symbol \mathcal{F} indicates the Fourier transform while \angle represents the phase of a complex number. The letter k is the generic Fourier spectral line while M indicates the maximum number of Fourier spectral lines taken into account for the analysis. N is the number of sampling points in each reflected spectra while $\delta\lambda = \lambda_{i+1} - \lambda_i$ is the wavelength resolution. Compared to other peak tracking algorithms, the FPC offers several benefits. Firstly, it produces precise and accurate results even when the wavelength resolution is poor and/or the reflected peak is noisy or partially distorted. Secondly, the FPC has a very high execution speed, therefore it can be used for dynamic sensing applications where continuous monitoring is required. Finally, when employed for obtaining

strain frequency response functions, the FPC allows to achieve higher SNR levels than other methods. A detailed analysis of the FPC algorithm and its performance is contained in [11,12].

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 The composite test beam

Figure 2 shows the schematic of the test beam used for this research. The beam was manufactured

Figure 2: Schematic of the composite beam with two FBG sensors embedded and one delamination: perspective view (a); lateral view of the region close to the delamination (b).

by assembling two different carbon fibre reinforced (CFR) laminated parts, indicated by L and S in Figure 2. Both parts are made using the same M10/T300 unidirectional pre-impregnated (prepreg) layers of carbon fibres. However, they differ for size and stacking sequence. Part L is 50 cm long and 4 cm wide and has a stacking sequence of $[0/90/0/90/0]_s$. Part S is as wide as L but it is 35 cm long and is formed by 16 layers of carbon fibres oriented at 0 degree. In both layups, the carbon fibres at 0 degrees are aligned with the direction of the beam maximum dimension. Two optical fibres are embedded between the 2nd and 3rd layer of part S. They are indicated in Figure 2 as FBG1 and FBG2. Both fibres are Draw Tower fibre Bragg gratings (DTG®) provided by FBGS-Technologies GmbH. DTGs are a particular type of FBGs. They have higher strength than common FBGs owing to their manufacturing process which consists in simultaneously drawing the fibre, writing the grating and coating the fibre directly after the grating inscription. The 2 FBGs used in this research have grating length of 8 mm, core diameter of 6 μm and cladding diameter 125 μm . It is worth to notice that the optical fibres were embedded parallel to the carbon fibre reinforcements of the S laminate since this has been proven to minimize the perturbation introduced in the host material [14]. In addition, the fibres were protected at their egresses by means of a Teflon tubing having a diameter of 500 μm (Figure2).

To create the delamination, a Teflon sheet of 6.5 cm x 4 cm has been inserted between S and L while assembling them. Figure 2b shows the relative position of the two FBG sensors with respect the delamination after the assembling. Both sensors are placed two layers above the delamination plane. The distance between the delamination tip and the projection of the grating center point in the delamination plane is about 2 cm for FBG1 and 4 cm for FBG2. After the assembling, the beam was cured in autoclave at 120 degrees Celsius. The beam was successively trimmed and its lateral edges were white painted and marked with a graduated scale in order to allow better visual inspection of the delamination extension. After the curing the two FBGs resulted to have Bragg wavelengths of 1536.35 nm (FBG1) and 1556.07 nm (FBG2). Figure 3 shows the manufactured beam.

Figure 3: Carbon fibre reinforced beam used for the experiments.

3.1 Experimental set up and automated experimental procedure

Figure 4 illustrates the experimental setup adopted to test the manufactured composite beam. An opportunely designed rigid support in steel was employed to clamp the first 14 cm of the beam bottom side. The beam top side was instead attached to an electro-mechanical shaker by means of two connection steel slats and a pin. An eccentric connection was created in order to be able to apply combined bending and torsion loads and therefore induce higher stress concentration at the delamination interface. The electro-mechanical shaker was voltage drive by an amplifier who received a computer generated signal through a NI USB-6341 data acquisition card (NI DAQ). A commercially available FBG scan 700 interrogator was used to read out the reflected spectra of the two FBG sensors. The interrogator acquisition rate was controlled via a trigger signal generated in Matlab® and sent to the interrogator via the NI DAQ. An ICP® accelerometer was used to validate the results of the FBG sensors. The accelerometer mounted on the beam surface in correspondence of FBG1 position.

Figure 4: Experimental setup used to apply a cycling load on the composite beam and induce delamination propagation.

Figure 5 shows the experimental procedure adopted to make the delamination propagate under fatigue load and to monitor the beam modal frequencies. The procedure is divided in 4 steps. In the first step a 6 Hz sinusoidal signal lasting 128 seconds is generated in Matlab®, sent to the NI DAQ, amplified and then applied by the shaker to the test beam. In the second step the beam is excited for 8 seconds with a Schroeder-phased multisine up to a frequency of 450 Hz. During the excitation, the FBG 700 interrogator acquires and stores the FBGs reflected spectra with a sampling frequency of 1 kHz using an in-house developed LabVIEW code. The same sampling rate is used by the NI DAQ to measure and save the accelerations. In the third step the FBG spectra are demodulated using the FPC algorithm described in Section 2.2 and the time evolutions of the Bragg wavelengths are retrieved. The final step deals with the modal parameters estimation. In this step both the accelerations and the demodulated FBG signals are transformed from the time to the frequency domain using a fast Fourier transform (FFT) and fed to a polyreference least-square modal parameter estimator [13]. Once the

estimated natural frequencies are stored, the procedure is repeated from the first step. This procedure allows to monitor changes in the natural frequencies approximately every 2 minutes.

Figure 5: The 4 steps of the experimental procedure used for monitoring the beam natural frequencies. N_s indicates the number of times the procedure is applied.

It is important to notice that, the advantage of the experimental procedure proposed in this research consists in using a single control platform (Matlab) and in being fully automated. In fact, the Matlab script developed in this study is capable to simultaneously control the shaker, the FBG interrogator and the accelerometer. Moreover, it is able to autonomously track changes in structural parameters by processing strain measurements in real time.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The procedure presented in Figure 5 was repeated $N_s = 110$ times. For each of these N_s repetitions the composite beam underwent 768 fatigue load cycles, which means that the total number of fatigue load cycles was 84480. For the first $N_s = 10$ repetitions, the amplitude of the fatigue load signal was set close to zero, in order to avoid the delamination propagation. Then, for $11 \leq N_s \leq 90$, the amplitude of the fatigue load cycles was increased to 8 V. Finally, for $91 \leq N_s \leq 110$, the signal amplitude was again decreased to almost zero.

Figure 6: Estimated beam modal frequencies obtained from the FBG. The top row shows three stabilization charts corresponding to different N_s values. The bottom row shows the evolution of the modal frequencies (black circles) and the delamination growth (green squares) as function of N_s .

The beam modal frequencies were estimated after each repetition (i.e. after 769 fatigue cycles) during the entire duration of the experiment. The bottom row of Figure 6 reports the evolution of the beam modal frequencies as function of the number of repetitions N_s estimated using the FBG measurements. The same plot shows the delamination propagation as N_s increases. The delamination growth was obtained by visually inspect the beam lateral side.

The upper row of Figure 6 shows the stabilization charts obtained by means of the polyreference estimator at $N_s = 1$ (initial condition), $N_s = 55$ (42240 fatigue cycles) and $N_s = 110$ (final condition). The beam modal frequencies estimated at the initial condition where $f_1 = 139.93$ Hz, $f_2 = 199.63$ Hz, $f_3 = 223.9$ Hz, $f_4 = 242.21$ Hz and $f_5 = 283.29$ Hz. The estimation of f_4 was often unstable so f_4 was not considered for the analysis. The accuracy on the estimation of each of the remaining 4 modal frequencies was obtained by computing the standard deviation σ of the estimates retrieved during the first 10 repetitions ($1 \leq N_s \leq 10$). The computed values were $\sigma_{f_1} = 0.05$, $\sigma_{f_2} = 0.18$, $\sigma_{f_3} = 0.12$ and $\sigma_{f_5} = 0.13$. The accuracy intervals provide statistical information on whether or not the frequency shifts are associated to possible damage propagation. In fact, if the frequencies estimated at a given N_s fall out of their $\pm\sigma$ bounds, then the chances of delamination propagation are equal to 66%. Figure 7 shows the shifts in modal frequencies f_1 , f_2 , f_3 and f_5 versus the number of loading repetitions N_s . For each frequency, the respective $\pm\sigma$ interval (dashed red line) around the mean of the first 10 estimations is also indicated.

Figure 7: Evolution of the beam modal frequencies and confidence intervals.

From the comparative analysis of Figures 6 and 7 it is possible to observe that:

- i. The delamination size remains unchanged for $N_s \leq 10$, since a very low amplitude load is applied. For $11 \leq N_s \leq 90$, the delamination grows almost linearly and reaches the final length of 15.1 cm.

- ii. The beam modal frequencies all decrease as the delamination propagates. The percentage decrease between initial and final condition is 6.03% for f_1 , 2.79% for f_2 , 5.15% for f_3 and 4.74% for f_5 . Except for f_3 , all the other frequencies shows a non-monotonic decreasing, with a jump occurring at $N_s = 32$ and corresponding to a delamination length of approximately 8.5 cm. The discontinuity is more evident for the first modal frequency. According to the authors, this behavior might be due to changes in the input forces caused by the high coupling between the composite beam and the shaker. Additional tests are therefore required for a better understanding of this phenomenon.
- iii. The second natural frequency f_2 has larger confidence bounds, therefore it is less capable to detect early stage delamination propagation compared to the other frequencies. On the contrary, f_1 estimates exhibit the lowest variability (i.e. minimum σ) therefore it is suitable for detecting small structural alterations.

Figure 8 reports the comparison between the modal frequencies estimated via the FBG sensors and those obtained through acceleration measurements. The accelerometer provides only 3 natural frequencies, which matches very good with the FBG frequencies f_1 , f_2 and f_5 . However, the acceleration based modal analysis is unable to estimate f_3 and f_4 . This might be related to the fact that: i.) only one accelerometer is used for the analysis; ii.) the accelerometer position might coincide to the nodal points of the modes corresponding to f_3 and f_4 .

Figure 8: Comparison between FBG (black circles) and accelerometer (red dots) measurements.

5 CONCLUSIVE REMARKS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

In this paper we investigated the feasibility of using modal analysis combined with embedded fibre Bragg grating sensors to detect propagating delamination in beamlike composite structures. We performed experiments on a CFR beam carrying an initial delamination and instrumented with two embedded FBGs and one surface mounted PCB accelerometer. Using an electro-mechanical shaker, we were able to make the delamination propagate under the effect of a fatigue load. At the same time, we were able to monitor the changes induced in the beam natural frequencies. We showed that the FBG sensors provide similar or even better results than accelerometers, with the additional benefit of being much less intrusive. The proposed fully automated methodology appears to be appropriate to monitor stiffness changes of real life structures. It offers many advantages: it is easy to implement, it allows to control multiple devices and sensing systems within a single platform, it is cost effective and it can be also applied to relatively large structure in operating conditions. The main drawback of the method is that it can not be used for damage localization purposes. However, the multiplexing capabilities of FBG sensors might offer a valid solution to such limitation. Future work will focus on

the use of similar structures but carrying embedded optical fibres with more Bragg gratings opportunely multiplexed. The modal parameter technique will then be extended to the estimation of the strain mode shapes which should increase the methodology performance by providing more information about the damage location.

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